

L'esprit libéral du Coran

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Islamic Traditions, Sunni, Text, Islamic modernization, Islamic Theology, Islam in Africa

Composed by César Benattar, el-Hadi Sebaï and Abdelaziz Ettéalbi, this book intended to portray Islam as a liberal religion by presenting its readers (mainly European and, most particularly, French men) with an interpretation of the Qur'an and the ahadith (أحاديث) that aligned with liberal philosophies. The book was published in the wake of the French colonization of Morocco, an event described in the introduction as a "pacifist penetration" intended to bring "enlightenment" to the Moroccan people, which helps us better frame the work according to its author's baselines. It was originally published in French and remained somewhat in vogue for the first few decades of the Protectorate, when al-Tha'albi (الثعالبي) was leader of the Destour Party (الحزب الحر الدستوري). Upon his exile to France, the book at hand silently fell into oblivion, but we have chosen to keep the dates covered up until the final years of the Protectorate in order to reflect this view that some people still referred to the work despite the fact that it was not so relevant anymore.

Date Range: 1905 CE - 1956 CE

Region: Tunisia

Region tags: Africa, Northern Africa, Tunisia

Tunisia

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite

Sources and Corpora

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://archive.org/details/LespritLiberalDuCoran/>

– Source 1 Description: Original text, as published in French.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Corrections

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: At the time of publication and composition, César Benattar was Correspondent of the Ministry of Public Instruction, el-Hadi Sebaï was former Secretary of the Tunisian Government as well as former interpreter at the Driba courts and al-Tha'albi was a journalist. Taking this into consideration, despite the fact that neither Benattar nor Sebaï were paid explicitly to write and publish the text at hand, they did get a salary from the government.

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– No

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– No

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– No

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– No

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Notes: The book was intended to be read by people in government positions in the French government (both mainland and colonial).

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: Even in the preface it is made clear that the authors understand that "wrong" and inherently "bad" interpretations of Qur'an and ahadith have caused Islam to become stagnant and reap an external reputation of being authoritarian, outdated and contrary to liberal philosophy. As a result, the whole book aims to present it under a "new" light in an effort to please the French while trying to awaken the Tunisians (and all Muslims, in general) to new interpretations that are portrayed as being more aligned with God's real message. Although Muslims were not intended as the main readership, the book did stem from a reformist vision.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: Because the text was not intended for a Muslim readership, it did have little to no impact in common interpretations of the shari'a (شريعة) in Tunisian courts.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: Although the idea of the Islamic calendar is present in the minds of the authors, it is irrelevant to the text at hand.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– No

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– I don't know

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

Notes: Of the many debates surrounding this topic in Islam, the text at hand only (slightly) engages with those that incorporate a gender component to them. In particular, the text mentions the idea that female and male souls are to be regarded and described as being equal to God, whereas bodies differ. Not enough details are mentioned and the issue is only written about in passing, so it appears not to have been a topic of great importance to the authors.

Reference: Sebaï, El-Hadi, César Benattar, and Abdelaziz Ettéalbi. *L'esprit Libéral Du Coran*. Paris: Ernest Leroux Éditeur, n.d.. <https://archive.org/details/LespritLiberalDuCoran>. p.31

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– Yes

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– I don't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Yes

Notes: In fact, the text at hand engages with said debate quite vehemently.

↳ What are the historically mainstream positions in the debate?

– Specify: The text at hand only talks about sufism with regards to this debate. The idea present in the book is that sufism and maraboutism were hugely influential in the Tunisian society of the time, almost appearing as "the only possible interpretation", and that each order or tariqa (طريقة) insisted that reverencing their founders or special members among their ranks would grant followers instant access to Heaven after death.

Reference: Sebaï, El-Hadi, César Benattar, and Abdelaziz Ettéalbi. *L'esprit Libéral Du Coran*. Paris: Ernest Leroux Éditeur, n.d..

<https://archive.org/details/LespritLiberalDuCoran>. p.50, p.56-57

↳ What are the historically minority positions?

– Specify: The text positions itself as a part in this supposedly minority opinion that is

contrary to the sufi view of access to Heaven being granted through certain actions in life, almost all of which involve revering a sufi leader or murshid (مرشد)..

Reference: Sebaï, El-Hadi, César Benattar, and Abdelaziz Ettéalbi. *L'esprit Libéral Du Coran*. Paris: Ernest Leroux Éditeur, n.d..

<https://archive.org/details/LespritLiberalDuCoran>. p.59

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: They are only mentioned in passing while talking about invoking the name of God.

Reference: Sebaï, el-Hadi, César Benattar, and Abdelaziz Ettéalbi. *L'esprit Libéral Du Coran*. Paris: Ernest Leroux Éditeur, n.d.. p.67

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: God is all-knowing.

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

|

- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - I don't know
 - Notes: The text does not go into details, but it is implied that God did communicate with humanbeings through the Qur'an, but nothing more is stated.
- ↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
 - No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Notes: The text makes no mention to either angels or junun (جنون).

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular
– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?
– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
– Yes

↳ Adultery
– Yes

↳ Incest
– Yes

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].
– Yes

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)
– Yes

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?
– No

↳ Other sexual practices
– Yes

Notes: Only heterosexual relationships are permitted.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: However, this issue is not clearly specified in the text as it is not the main interest of the authors.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

Notes: Considering that the text insists that the "generally accepted interpretation of God's words" is wrong, the text does imply that punishments and rewards do not conform to existing societal norms, but rather to God's original intentions.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group

– No

↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Notes: However, this issue is not clearly specified in the text as it is not the main interest of the authors.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - No
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
 - No
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?
 - No
 - ↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Consists of eternal happiness?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?
 - No
 - ↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?
 - I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

- Are messianic beliefs present in the text?
 - No

- Is an eschatology present in the text?
 - No

Norms & Moral Realism

- Are general social norms prescribed by the text?
 - Yes

- Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?
 - Yes

- ↳ What is the nature of this distinction?
 - Strongly present & highlighted

- ↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?
 - Yes

Reference: Sebaï, El-Hadi, César Benattar, and Abdelaziz Ettéalbi. *L'esprit Libéral Du Coran*. Paris: Ernest Leroux Éditeur, n.d.. <https://archive.org/details/LespritLiberalDuCoran>. p.19-29

- ↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts
 - No

- ↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities
 - No

- ↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)
 - No

- ↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– Yes

Notes: In fact, the text talks about the problems caused by the wrong interpretation of said societal, moral norms to be linked to God's command when, according to the authors, the two were not linked.

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– Only one gender

Notes: The social norms described in the text all revolve around the veil and social seclusion and, as such, they only apply to Muslim women.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Since the text is not a traditional religious text, but rather an essay touching on certain religious interpretations and/or social customs, it only highlights some of the moral virtues typically associated with Islam.

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

- ↳ Generosity/charity
 - No
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - No
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - No
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - No
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - No
- ↳ Cooperation
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - Yes
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - No
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - No

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

↳ Humility/modesty

– No

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– No

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The text does not touch upon issues such as sex, marriage, family, etc.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– I don't know

Notes: Despite not talking about it, it is to be supposed that only the sexual relationships considered to be approved by Islam are accepted.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Notes: Again, the text doesn't talk about fasting although it is an Islamic requirement. This is not to say that the text believes the practice should be stopped, but rather that it is not interesting to the authors, hence it is not mentioned.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Notes: It is not a requisite, but the ideas described in the text were considered to go against the norm of the times (for example, with regards to women's veiling practices and sufism), so it did cause a backlash from conservative elements of society against the authors.

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A state

Notes: At this point in time, Tunisia was under the control of the French, even as the Ottoman Empire retained nominal sovereignty. However, it was perceived as an autonomous region by the members writing the text (all of whom had nationalist inclinations), hence the choice of "state" as a description.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Except for al-Tha'albi, the other two authors were or had been government employees. They all came from the political and learned elite of the time.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text talks about education, particularly with regards to women.

Reference: Sebaï, El-Hadi, César Benattar, and Abdelaziz Ettéalbi. *L'esprit Libéral Du Coran*. Paris: Ernest Leroux Éditeur, n.d.. <https://archive.org/details/LespritLiberalDuCoran>. p.30, p.95

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– Yes

Notes: The text merely touches on the issue that, if only religious education based on wrongful interpretations of the Qur'an is available to the people, then the nation will never prosper.

Reference: Sebaï, El-Hadi, César Benattar, and Abdelaziz Ettéalbi. *L'esprit Libéral Du Coran*. Paris: Ernest Leroux Éditeur, n.d.. <https://archive.org/details/LespritLiberalDuCoran>. p.75

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– I don't know

Notes: The text talks about the then current situation of women being mostly barred from education and makes a point of opening opportunities for women to receive education. However, it never elaborates on whether education should be segregated between sexes and genders.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Regarding larger textual traditions yes, it was mostly only ever available to men. Regarding this particular text, please refer to previous note.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Notes: Education is seen as the main element in progressing and thriving as a society and a religion all throughout the text.

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: Most mentions to warfare refer to the rocky relationship between Islam and other faiths (namely Christianity and Judaism) and portray it as another misinterpretation of the Qur'an. According to the authors, religion wars are actually against the Qur'an and Muslim people should neither force their religion onto others nor fight others for their differences in faith.

Reference: Sebaï, El-Hadi, César Benattar, and Abdelaziz Ettéalbi. *L'esprit Libéral Du Coran*. Paris: Ernest Leroux Éditeur, n.d.. <https://archive.org/details/LespritLiberalDuCoran>. p.32-33

Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military

force?

– I don't know

Notes: Technically no, but the preface talks openly about the invasion of Morocco by France and presses the former to submit to the latter on the basis of the French being more knowledgeable and socially advanced.

Reference: Sebaï, El-Hadi, César Benattar, and Abdelaziz Ettéalbi. *L'esprit Libéral Du Coran*. Paris: Ernest Leroux Éditeur, n.d.. <https://archive.org/details/LespritLiberalDuCoran>. p.10

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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Reference: *L'esprit libéral du Coran*, Marzouki, Ilhem. *Le Mouvement Des Femmes En Tunisie Au Xxème Siècle*. Paris: Maisonneuve et Larose, n.d..

Reference: *L'esprit libéral du Coran*, Pérez-Beltrán, Carmelo. "Panorámica Sobre El Status Social De La Mujer Magrebi". *Miscelánea De Estudios Árabes E Islámicos: Sección Árabe-islam* 40 (n.d.).

Reference: *L'esprit libéral du Coran*, Murphy, Emma C.. "Women in Tunisia: Between State Feminism and

Economic Reform". In *Women and Globalization in the Arab Middle East*. Colorado and London: Lynne Rienner, n.d..

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